

A STUDY ON INFLUENCE OF OCCUPATIONAL STRESS ON WOMEN TEACHERS IN SELF FINANCE INSTITUTIONS WITH REFERENCE TO ERODE DISTRICT

Dr. E. T. Lokganathan* & G. Gomathi**

* Associate Professor, Department of Corporate Secretaryship with CA, Kongu Arts and Science College (Autonomous), Erode, Tamilnadu

** Assistant Professor, Department of Corporate Secretaryship with CA, Kongu Arts and Science College (Autonomous), Erode, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Dr. E. T. Lokganathan & G. Gomathi, "A Study on Influence of Occupational Stress on Women Teachers in Self Finance Institutions with Reference to Erode District", International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education, Volume 4, Issue 1, Page Number 1-5, 2019.

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Abstract:

Occupation stress has negative consequence on work performance of women teachers. The motive of the study is to evaluate the influence of occupational stress on women teachers in higher educational institutions. A total of 100 women faculty members contributed their views on occupational stress in their job. Data has been collected by providing well-structured questionnaire among the women faculty members. This study employed descriptive research design to interpret results and used simple random sampling to select samples. Percentage analysis, rotated component matrix and Friedman test are used to analyze the data. Results found that faculty members largely influenced by stressors like workplace compulsions, personal problems, academic performance, teaching methodology, and development works. It was found that physical exercises, meditation, and healthy food consumption are the effective stress coping method to the women faculty members working in higher educational institutions. It was concluded that women faculty members in higher educational institutions facing high level of occupational stress.

Key Words: Higher Education, Women Teachers, Occupational Stress, Stress Coping Strategies & Impact of Stress

1. Introduction:

India has a distinction nature of higher education system, which consists of pure government institutions, pure private institutions and government aided institutions managed by the private trust. Indian higher education sector follows different syllabus system and it is developing the way of education to satisfy the different requirements of industries. Frequently, government implements new policy framework to promote higher education in order to equip relevant skills by the learners. Indian higher education sector is seeking to implement vast changes in institutional functioning, infrastructure, quality of faculty, and so on. Therefore, structural changes in higher education lead to impart heavy workload, which ultimately ends with occupation stress among the teachers. Private higher educational institutions assign more responsibilities to their faculty members. Both male and female teachers have to face occupational stress equally in the workplace. No leniency is provided to the women faculty by considering their gender. Women faculty has to deliver dual role both in family and workplace. Therefore, existence of higher workload and other workplace restrictions creates occupational stress to the women teachers.

2. Statement of the Problem:

Women teacher has to deliver different role as an employee, parent, wife, daughter, and a responsible citizen. Teaching is a complex nature of work to the women teacher, especially in higher educational institutions. Teachers have to give lecture, develop students' skills, evaluate their performance, and perform management tasks along with have to honour family responsibilities. Occupational stress in teaching profession is an unavoidable phenomenon. It happens due to difference between occupational expectations and personal capacities to perform in the workplace. Educational institutions are transforming from traditional way of education to modern education pattern. The sources of stress to women teachers are mainly in the form of heavy workload, deadlines, lack of recognition, inadequate salary and so forth. Some amount of stress is required to motivate the teaching community, but excessive stress affects the performance of employees. Stress can be viewed as psycho-physical aspect which influences performance, efficiency, productivity of the teachers. Moreover, prevalence of excessive stress may reduce personal health and quality of work. It was found that teaching profession is considered as highly stressful occupation, which destructively influences teachers' health and consecutively dampers learning outcome of students. In this way, women teaching community face lot of occupational stress especially the married women have to render dual role in family and workplace. Therefore, this study can be initiated to check the influence of occupational stress on women teachers in higher educational institutions.

3. Review of Literature:

This study presents earlier review of literature concerning different facets of occupational stress. Vijayashree & Mund (2011) revealed that stress is now frequently called as a reaction of physical or emotional pressure and a feeling of being not capable to deal with anxiety and uneasiness, predominantly in relation to change. Anbuchelvan (2010) revealed that there is significant difference exist between men and women teachers with respect to occupational stress. Moreover, there is no significant difference among the men and women teachers with respect to their marital status, area of residence, teaching experience and educational qualification. Dua & Sangwan (2017) found that women teachers are more susceptible to stress. The volume of stress is caused by numerous factors together with poor working situations, intense workloads, shortage of resources, and lack of managerial and family support system. Consequently, these stressful features of teaching, stress can have unenthusiastic causes on mental, behavioural, emotional, and physical wellbeing of the teachers.

Bhuvaneshwari (2013) attempted to conduct a case study on psychological and physiological stress experienced by married working women faculties in different teaching institutions. Results of the study showed that stress among married working women is resulted because of a mixture of family and work commitments, extensive working hours, nuisances and inappropriate work life balance. Prevailing excessive stress leads to different problems such as prolonged headaches, hypertension and flabbiness. Reddy and Poornima (2012) revealed that occupational stress of the teachers have been correlated to high absenteeism, more attrition, low productivity, low morale and other negative organizational influences. Sabherwal Ahuja (2015) has tried to examine the level of occupational stress among faculty members in higher educational institutions. The results revealed that the determinants of stress among the teachers are different and numerous, time deadline, lack of resource accessibility, in-disciplinary activities of students, poor salary are the most significant stressors.

4. Objectives of the Study:

This study has been started with the following specific objectives:

- To describe the personal profile of the women faculty members in higher education institutions.
- To examine the factors influencing occupational stress of women faculty members in higher educational institutions.
- To suggest the suitable stress coping strategies to the women faculty members employed in higher educational institutions.

5. Research Methodology:

This study has been initiated to assess the level of occupational stress involved on women faculty members working in higher educational institutions. This study has been formulated on the strength of descriptive research design. The target population of the study consists of women faculty members working in arts and science colleges, engineering institutions, medical science institutions, and b-schools in Erode district. The study planned to collect data from all cadres of faculty members, head of department, dean or director, and so on. Women faculty members with more than 1 year of experience and wide exposure in academic work are considered for data collection. The sample size consists of 100 women faculty members and it ensures participation ratio of 100%. Questionnaire has been deployed as survey instrument to collect data from the respondents. Data is collected by providing structured questionnaire among the respondents. The survey instrument intends to assess the factors contributing to occupational stress in the higher educational institutions. Initially, the survey instrument was pre-tested with 15 faculty members in the sample area. Based on the results of pre-test, important changes such as, words formation and changes in information content has been carried out in the final survey instrument. The content validity of the questionnaire is tested with the professionals and experts in occupation stress in human resource domain. This study widely used percentage analysis, rotated component matrix, and Friedman chi-square test used for analysis of data.

6. Results and Discussions:

6.1 Analysis of Personal Profile:

The personal profile of women faculty members is scrutinized and its results are presented in table-1.

Table 1: Personal Profile of Respondents

Profile	Distribution	Sample	Frequency
Age	Less than 25 years	12	12%
	26 – 35 years	43	43%
	36 – 50 years	38	38%
	More than 51 years	7	7%
Educational Qualification	Post Graduation	37	37%
	M.Phil	42	42%
	SLET/ NET	11	11%
	Doctoral Degree	10	10%
Experience	1 – 3 years	18	18%
	3 – 5 years	34	34%
	5 – 10 years	32	32%

	More than 10 years	16	16%
Monthly Salary	Below 30,000	39	39%
	30,001 – 50,000	34	34%
	50,001 – 70,000	19	19%
	70,001 & above	8	8%
Designation	Assistant Professor	49	49%
	Associate Professor	26	26%
	Professor	14	14%
	Head/Dean/Director	11	11%
Working Institution	Arts & Science	42	48%
	Management	5	5%
	Engineering	36	36%
	Medical Science	17	11%

(Source: Primary Data)

It is found that in table 1, age of the respondents furnishes that 12% are in less than 25 years of age, 43% are in 26-35 years, 38% are in 36-50 years, and 7% are in more than 51 and years. Educational qualification reveals that 37% are completed post graduation, 42% are completed M.Phil, 11% are SLET/ NET qualified and rest 10% are completed doctoral degree in their domain. Experience furnishes that 18% are having experience of 1-3 years, 34% are experienced in 3-5 years, 32% are having experience of 5-10 years and rest 16% are experienced in more than 10 years. Monthly salary shows that 39% are drawing monthly salary of below Rs.10,000, 34% are getting salary between Rs.10,001 – 20,000 per month, 19% are drawing salary between Rs.20,001 – 40,000 per month, and rest 8% are getting salary of Rs.40,001 and above. Designation reveals that 49% are working as assistant professor, 26% are working in the cadre of associate professor, 14% are working as professor and 11% are working as head/dean/director. Working institution shows that 42% are employed in arts and science institutions, 5% are employed in management schools, 36% are working in engineering institutions, and 17% are employee medical science institutions like pharmacy, nursing, dental and paramedical institutions.

6.2 Factors Influencing Occupational Stress:

The following rotated component matrix has been conducted to examine the factors causing occupational stress of women faculty members. This study identified twenty-seven factors and it is provided on five Point Likert-type scales ranging from '1' as not important to '5' highly important. In order to check that factors that influenced on women faculty member mostly in their work place that is, '1' for not important '2' for least important, '3' for important, '4' for most important and '5' for highly important. The results of rotated component matrix are provided in table-2.

Table 2: Rotated Component Matrix

Label	Factors	Workplace Compulsions	Personal Problems	Academic Performance	Teaching Methodology	Development works
OS21	High workload	.835	.063	.143	.126	.125
OS23	Adamant behavior of students	.821	-.048	.093	.093	.063
OS13	Lack of performance appraisal	.797	.022	.047	-.028	.084
OS24	Poor relationship with colleagues	.772	.031	.154	.035	.112
OS15	Pressure to perform	.745	.129	.110	-.005	.084
OS01	Working atmosphere	.646	-.045	.039	.009	.076
OS04	Workplace harassment	.799	.011	.119	.160	.101
OS14	No recognition	.183	.677	.043	-.056	.164
OS25	Admission pressure	.097	.644	.135	.049	-.093
OS10	Low level of salary	.164	.612	.114	.101	.150
OS05	Work life imbalance	.202	.601	.052	.124	.098
OS16	Lack of management support	.197	.586	.056	.034	.064
OS12	Family problems	.163	.558	.146	.055	-.043
OS06	Health problems	.194	.514	.132	.096	.091
OS03	Not able to care family affairs	.146	.505	.077	.134	.124
OS07	High level of non-academic work	.081	.118	.757	.107	.110
OS17	No job security	.156	.104	.723	.215	.094
OS02	Deadlines	.167	.087	.626	.201	.311

OS18	Students performance in examination	.172	.254	.544	-.021	-.041
OS26	Lack of pedagogical skills	.156	.016	-.024	.792	.368
OS19	Course curriculum	.134	.163	.083	.731	.184
OS09	No career growth	.098	.256	.097	.672	.101
OS08	Poor job design	.026	.053	.117	.567	.056
OS20	Publication compulsions	.150	.072	.083	.212	.802
OS11	High torture	.052	-.012	.103	.216	.745
OS27	Development work	.029	-.033	.053	.169	.683
OS22	Committee work	.063	-.044	.079	.156	.619
	Eigen values	6.425	4.216	2.534	1.734	1.094
	% Variance	17.346	12.164	10.753	8.636	7.573
	Cumulative % Variance	17.346	29.510	40.263	48.899	56.472
	Cronbach's α	0.7267	0.7171	0.7988	0.6575	0.5578

(Source: Primary Data)

Table 2 reveals the rotated component matrix with factor loading that are extracted and regarded as relevant to the construct indicated in bold. The cut-off rate for factor loading is assigned as 0.5. The exploratory factor analysis presents the twenty-seven characteristics on occupational stress of women faculty members. The factors are collectively accounts for cumulative variance of 56.472% explained in the data. The Cronbach's alpha values for the factors advocate good reliability values that is, $\alpha > 0.5$. Workplace compulsion is the main factor that women faculty members have observed this factor as the most important factor with the highest explained variance of 17.346%. Seven variables loaded in this factor like, high workload, adamant behaviour of students, lack of performance appraisal, poor relationship with colleagues, pressure to perform, working atmosphere, and workplace harassment. Workplace compulsions are the highest cause for occupational stress among women faculty members in higher educational institutions.

Personal problems have been considered as second most important factor with the explained variance of 12.164%. Eight components have been loaded on this factors, which includes no recognition, admission pressure, low salary, work life imbalance, lack of management support, family problems, personal problems, and not able to care family affairs. This factor is considered as most significant factor in influencing occupational stress to women faculty members. Academic performance is the third most significant factors, which explains 10.753% variance in data. It is loaded with four variables such as, high level of non-academic work, no job security, deadlines, and students' performance in examination. Teaching methodology is the fourth factor on which four variables such as, lack of pedagogical skills, course curriculum, no career growth, and poor job design are loaded and together accounts for 8.636% variance in data. Finally, development works loaded with four variables like publication compulsions, high torture, development work, and committee work, which together explains 7.573% variance in data.

6.3. Stress Coping Strategies:

Stress coping strategies should be required to enhance performance of women faculty members. Women faculty members are highly affected due to both academic and non-academic works. In order to assess the different strategies to cope stress, Friedman chi-square test has been administered. The null hypothesis states that the ranks of stress coping strategies are not different from its expected value. The results are provided in table 3.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

Stress Coping Strategies	N	Mean Rank	Mean Score	Std. Deviation	Chi-Square
Physical exercises	100	10.91	3.164	1.5432	141.862 P value 0.00*
Counseling for solutions		7.71	2.893	1.2874	
Watching televisions		6.90	2.436	1.6285	
Healthy food consumption		9.69	2.374	1.2495	
Listening music		7.43	3.437	1.5547	
Meditation/yoga		9.82	2.652	1.2263	
Playing games		5.73	2.568	1.5474	
Reading books		6.98	3.236	1.2436	
Sharing problems with others		7.53	3.036	1.1274	
Absence of work		5.98	2.753	1.3437	
Talking with friends		6.63	3.191	1.5254	
Relaxation		8.54	3.173	1.3453	
Sportive attitude		8.19	3.153	1.1237	
Positive thinking		5.97	2.625	1.2621	
Outing with family		6.41	2.364	1.5282	

(Source: Primary Data)

* Significant at 1% level

Table 3 reveals the results of Friedman's test, under this ranking the value of chi-square is 141.862. The degrees of freedom are up to the number of variables less than 1, the asymptotic significant is the measured probability of attaining factors is not statistically different. Therefore, results of chi-square with 15 degrees of freedom are unexpectedly occurred by change. It could be evident that among the fifteen factors, physical exercises (10.91) is ranked first; it is followed by meditation/yoga (9.82), healthy food consumption (9.69), relaxation (8.54), sportive attitude (8.19), counselling for solutions (7.71), sharing problems with others (7.53), and listening music (7.43) are ranked consequently from second to eighth respectively. Furthermore, reading books (6.98), watching televisions (6.90), talking with friends (6.43), outing with family (6.41), absence of work (5.98), positive thinking (5.97), and playing games (5.73) are ranked from ninth to fifteenth respectively. It can be suggested that physical exercises, meditation, and healthy food consumption are the effective stress coping method to the women faculty members working in higher educational institutions. It is inferred that these factors are effective stress coping strategies to women faculty members.

7. Conclusion:

Women teachers are highly exposed to stress in their regular working environment, which has harmful effect on their personal health. Due to the excessive stress they are not able to develop their skills and it significantly erodes performance. Women teachers regardless of their regular teaching, they face personal, family and professional problems, which heavily influence their wellbeing. Findings from the percentage analysis shows that majority of respondents (43%) were in the age group of 26-35 years. Educational qualification revealed that 42% are completed M.Phil degree, 39% of faculty member's salary falls less than Rs.10,000 per month. Designation showed that 49% are working as assistant professor. Experience level revealed that 34% are experienced in 3-5 years and 42% are working in arts and science institutions. The exploratory factor analysis revealed that workplace compulsions, personal problems, academic performance, teaching methodology, and development works are causing for occupational stress to the women faculty members and put together explains 56.472% variance in data. The Cronbach's alphas for the factors suggest good reliability values i.e., $\alpha > 0.5$. It can be found that physical exercises, meditation, and healthy food consumption are the effective stress coping strategies to the women faculty members. It is concluded that women faculty members in higher educational institutions facing high level of occupational stress. It is suggested that management of private educational institutions should make effective measures to reduce occupational stress.

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